

Building a Caramia Brand Image Through Circular Model Instagram @Caramiastore at Social Media

Teguh Priyo Sadono

Universitas 17 Agustus 1945 Surabaya

Corresponding Author: Teguh Priyo Sadono teguhsadono@untag-sby.ac.id

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords: Marketing
Communication, Instagram,
Brand Image

Received : 3 November

Revised : 18 November

Accepted: 20 December

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ABSTRACT

Increasing in technology and information development in the world is currently now runs further and rapidly in a digital technology. It is also happened in ith developments in the field of communication technology. Instagram is one of the social media that is the most number of user in the world, there is also an increase in the number of users in Instagram, including business people who use Instagram as a marketing tool. This study aims to determine marketing communication strategies through Instagram social media in building a brand image on @Caramiastore. The method used is primary data with collecting data in the form of in-depth interviews. The results of the study show that the @caramiastore.id Instagram account has implemented a consistent marketing communication strategy through social media Instagram. The marketing communication strategy is carried out through consistent advertising, promotion, personal selling and public relations on the Instagram they manage in building a brand image

INTRODUCTION

Background Problem

In line with developments in technology and communication digital On the internet, social media continues to develop in features and benefits for each user. One of the social media that is widely used by people in Indonesia is Instagram. Instagram is a social media that is loved by many people. The users are very diverse, from children to parents. This social media, which focuses on photo and video sharing platforms, has skyrocketed in popularity to the point where it is comparable to Facebook and Twitter. Indonesia is recorded as having the fourth largest Instagram social media users in the world (Sendari, 2019).

Currently, more and more MSME entrepreneurs are taking advantage of the facilities digital, especially by utilizing social media, especially Instagram, as a marketing channel. This is also what the account does@caramiastore.id, an Instagram account that was originally a fashion seller online. Before using Instagram, Caramia store was actually already engaged in sales online through marketplace Shope with the same product. The use of the Instagram account @caramiastore.id has resulted in many new transactions or an increase in sales transactions compared to before. After managing the promotion and sales of pajama, Muslim clothing and other products which have been carried out through this channe lonline Of Marketplace Shopee. Business owners admit that Instagram has advantages, for example selling through Instagram frees managers from having to pay shop/shop rent or other costs that usually arise in conventional trading. That way, business owners make optimal use of all the features on Instagram.

This research is important to do because Caramiastore.id has previously used its marketplace Shopee. This shows that this business owner knows the special advantages of trading his products through the marketplace online. Trade online does not require a special place so the owner of this business is domiciled in Bojonegoro, which is a city located relatively far from the provincial capital. This business is also a relatively new business so it markets products through means digital or online can expand the market to all corners of Indonesia. Apart from the benefits that are attached to the business online. In fact, the development of Caramia Store's business is also very dependent on consumers who are looking for pajamas, while the number of consumers who urgently need pajamas is relatively small. Therefore, Caramia Store has experienced a slow increase in the number of buyers over time. Consumer tastes are also always evolving towards the latest models but with relatively cheap price options. Therefore, business owners see social media opportunities to develop their business even further. Based on the results of many studies, it is shown that the use of social media will cause an increase in brand image.

Brand image refers to the structured memory of a brand that exists in the minds of consumers. Brand image contains target market interpretations of product attributes, benefits, usage situations, users, and manufacturer/marketer characteristics. This is what people think and feel when they hear or see a brand. Essentially, it is a collection of associations that consumers have learned about a brand. Company image and store image are similar except they apply to companies and stores rather than brands. The importance of branding and brand

image can be seen from the fact that traditionally unbranded products such as water, apples and meat are increasingly becoming branded (Mothers baugh and Hawkins, 2018). Brand image is the consumer's perception of a brand which is described through brand associations that are embedded in consumer memory (Keller, 2013). Followed by Keller (2013), a brand with brand image positive ones find it easier to successfully market products even if there is a crisis or decline in brand fortunes.

Based on these definitions, it appears that Brand image is an important thing that every businessman must build and maintain. Also includes shops online shop @caramiastore.id. This shop uses Instagram and all activities on social media to build brand image. In the photos or images published on its Instagram page, @caramiastore.id tries to show the dominance of yellow. Furthermore, the yellow flower is also circled around the company logo which appears on the main page of the @caramiastore.id account. Apart from this, the @caramiastore.id logo also contains an illustration of a woman wearing a hat which impresses women who like it fashion. The choice of yellow which is highlighted in every @caramiastore.id activity on Instagram also symbolizes a graceful spirit that still prioritizes a youthful and creative appearance.

Various activities on Instagram, ranging from uploading photos, publishing new products, or quizzes are forms of marketing communication that appear to be efforts to build Brand image which is positive in the eyes of consumers. Through marketing communications on Instagram, buyers can easily communicate with @caramiastore.id as a seller of pajamas and Muslim clothing easily. Buyers are also expected to be able to easily understand everything about the product, for example: knowing what the product and goods are used for as a whole, can be consumed by anyone, how to get them, where the goods can be obtained, what the quality of the goods is, what the price is. offered, who to consult if there is a deviation in value, so that consumers feel that they are not wrong in using the product. Researchers chose marketing communications via Instagram as a specific strategy to improve Brand image. Based on the background of the problem above, the author conducted research, namely to find out "Marketing communication strategies via Instagram Social Media in Building Brand image Account @caramiastore.id"

Research Focus

The focus of this research is: namely building strategies Brand image caramia via social media Instagram at @Caramiastore

Problem Formulation

Based on the background of this research, the problem that will be researched now is "how Caramia SMEs develop brand image via the Instagram social media account @caramiastore.id?"

Research Purposes

Based on the background and problem formulation above, the aim to be achieved in this research is to find out "Caramia MSME strategies in developing brand image via Instagram account @Caramiastore"

Theoretical basis

In understanding the strategic steps taken by SME Caramia in building a brand image, it is necessary to understand more about the strategy which is the concept in this research. The strategy used in this research refers to the strategy terminology developed by Jauch and Glueck (2000) which states that strategy is a unified, comprehensive and integrated plan that links a company's advantages to environmental challenges and is designed to ensure that the company's main goals can be achieved through implementation. (Glueck, William F., and Jauch, Lawrence R. 2000. *Strategic Management and Company Policy* (2nd-ed). Jakarta. Erlangga.) If seen etymologically, it comes from the word Strategos in Greek which is formed from the word stratos or soldier and the word ego or leader. In Oxford Learner's Pocket Dictionaries (2010), Strategy (noun): a plan of action designed to achieve a long-term or overall aim. If translated into Indonesian, it means an action plan designed to achieve long-term or overall goals. (Kusumadmo, E. 2013. *Strategic Knowledge Management*. Yogyakarta: Cahaya Atma Pustaka) According to the 2007 Big Indonesian Dictionary (KBBI), based on the definition of strategy above, the definition of strategy in this research can be formulated as a tool to achieve company goals in relation to long-term goals, follow-up programs, and allocation priorities. resource. Meanwhile, communication strategy is understood as a business effort that uses communication tools to build understanding or mutual understanding between sources that produce communication symbols and those that receive communication symbols. In the context of this research, it is about building an understanding of communication between sellers and buyers in the marketing process, which is known as marketing communication.

Marketing Communications

Without communication between the seller and the buyer, there will certainly be no understanding between the seller and the buyer. The existence of products and services in the market or on the shop floor will result in intensive interaction when communication between those in the market does not occur. Communication between them is known as marketing communication. Thus, marketing communication has a very important purpose because it is a liaison between sellers and buyers so that in determining marketing communication it must be arranged systematically and can run efficiently. Aspects of marketing communication strategy according to Kotler (Aprilia, 2017)

- a) Advertising is the most effective way to influence the purchasing power of geographically dispersed consumers at a relatively low cost per display.
- b) Sales promotions or invitations to make purchase transactions that encourage stronger responses from consumers in the form of discounts and vouchers.
- c) The relationship between publicity and society is based on three special characteristics of credibility and society.

d) Personal selling is interaction between sellers and buyers via Instagram social media by personally contacting consumers. Personal selling is a very effective tool for building references for purchasing actions among consumers.

e) Direct marketing :Direct relationships with carefully targeted individual consumers to obtain immediate responses and build lasting customer relationships.

Options It is hoped that strategic choices such as those conveyed by Kloter in communication will be able to build product brands at the top of their customers, which of course will result in the act of purchasing the products offered. The process of creating brand equity begins with the formation of a positive brand image in the target market segment.

The circular model can be referred to by Charles E. Osgood and Wilbur Schramm, who developed circular theory by focusing on discussions on the behavior of the main actors in the communication process (Effendy, 2003). Osgood explained Shannon and Weaver's technical communication model in overcoming communication problems. This model is based more on the Theory of Meaning and psycholinguistics. This thinking sees each individual in communication as simultaneously functioning as a source and as a destination. Just as the transmitter and receiver process decode messages, they also code through a number of mechanical feedbacks. This circular model always refers to the presence of a feedback element, which means that the communication process does not start from one point and ends at another point. This communication process does not start from one point to another in a circular, full circle process. In Osgood's model, input is defined as some form of physical energy and stimulus that is encoded in a form that is modified by sensory impulses.

The receiver captures stimuli or input through reception and perception processes. Meanwhile, the transmitter, in Osgood's terminology, forms the motor of the organization and a series of activities. The message or response thus includes source output and destination input. Output is produced through encoding while input is obtained through decoding. Destination has a position parallel to the source. Osgood views that each individual in the communication process is seen as a complete communication system in accordance with Shannon and Weaver's model. Osgood then reconstructed Shannon's model as stated in the term communication unit consisting of a sender and recipient of a message. In this case, Osgood places emphasis on the social situation of communication by explaining that in several adequate models, at least two communication units are needed, namely the source unit (speaker) and the destination unit (heater). The two systems are connected by a single system called a message. In connection with the above, messages are part of the total input of a source unit, and at the same time are also part of the total input of the destination unit. In other words, the communicator and the communicant interact with each other in a participatory manner. (Effendy, Onong Uchjana. 2003. *Communication Science: Theory and Practice*. Bandung: PT Teen Rosdakarya)

Brand Image

Brand Image refers to the schematic memory of a brand. Brand image contains the target market's interpretation of product attributes, benefits, usage situations, users, and producer/marketer characteristics. Brand image is what people think and feel when they hear or see a brand name. Essentially, it is a set of associations that consumers have learned about a brand (Mothersbaugh and Hawkins 2018:337). This is in line with the opinion of Wijaya (2013) who stated that brand image can be assumed to be a set of brand associations collected in the minds of consumers. In simple terms, it can be said that brand image is actually what consumers think and feel when they hear or see a brand identity. Or in other words, brand image is a certain form or image of a trace of meaning left in the minds of the consumer audience.

Brand image is a major concern of both industrial and consumer goods marketers. A brand is more than a symbol that differentiates a product from other similar products. More than that, the brand also illustrates the manufacturer's promise to continuously deliver features, certain benefits and services to consumers. The image of a brand represents a perception that can reflect objective or subjective reality. The image formed from perceptual representation becomes the basis for making decisions to purchase a product and even to have brand loyalty (Wijaya, 2013).

Social Media

Mass communication is communication using mass media, of course the mass media in question is modern mass media. Mass communication involves a number of dispersed, heterogeneous, anonymous audiences with messages simultaneously and momentarily. Mass communication can be defined as a communication process that takes place when messages are sent from institutional sources to mass audiences through mechanical means such as radio, television, newspapers and films.

Mass communication messages go in one direction and the response back is slow (delayed) and very limited. However, with the faster development of communication technology, especially electronic mass media such as radio and television, feedback from the audience can be provided quickly to the communicator. Apart from that, the nature of spreading messages through direct mass media is very fast, simultaneously and widely. Social media is able to overcome distance and time and is long-lasting if documented. Meeting people you don't know (strangers), but because this media can make users connect and pay attention to their social networks. On some large social networking sites, members do not use the network to meet new people, but rather to communicate with people who are already part of their extended social network.

Instagram

Instagram is a social media that can be used as a direct marketing medium and to interact with consumers. The main use of Instagram is as a place to share photos by uploading them so that they can be seen by the public. The social system in this application involves becoming followers of each other's accounts. In this way, communication between fellow Instagram users can be established by giving likes and also commenting on photos that have been uploaded by other users. Therefore, teenagers, especially students nowadays, compete to upload the best photos by editing them half-heartedly and as well as possible before uploading so that they get lots of likes and the photo of the account owner becomes popular. In the activity of sharing these photos, users can not only share them on Instagram, but can also be shared on other social media via Instagram.

Basic Research Framework

For the sake of building brand image on the @caramiastore.id account on Instagram social media, one of the necessary communication strategies for marketing pajamas and Muslim clothing products on the @caramiastore.id account via Instagram social media is to carry out advertisements via posts on Instagram

Picture 1. Research Framework

LITERATURE REVIEW

Interactional Communication in marketing communication emphasizes direct involvement between traders and consumers in communication. This communication is considered the most effective in convincing consumers of the meaning of a trademark. Such communication can be understood in the concept of interactive communication. Where the parties involved in communication participate together in building shared meaning. Participatory communication is an inclusive dialogue model that provides opportunities for all parties involved in communication to express opinions, listen and be heard (Singhal & Devi, 2003). Thus, participatory communication will be formed in a circular communication frame from which the source will encode the message conveyed based on the source's interpretation and then become a signal for the recipient to decode the signal based on the recipient's interpretation to start the decoding process. When the source incode can be understood by the recipient with the same decode, mutual understanding will be formed. Such a communication process is known as a circular communication process, no longer a linear process in the Lasswell's model.

METHODOLOGY

Research Terminology

This research was prepared with the title "Marketing Communication Strategy Through Instagram Social Media in BuildingBrand image Account @Caramiastore.Id". Based on this title, the terminology that can be explained is: Strategy

1. The strategy referred to in this research is all the plans, steps and actions carried out by the @Caramiastore.Id account while running its business.

2. Marketing Communications.

Marketing communications referred to here are all steps in the form of actions to communicate products and the advantages and uniqueness of products marketed by the @Caramiastore.Id account. This marketing communication was transformed into an advertising strategy on Instagram by the account owner @Caramiastore.Id.

3. Instagram Social Media.

Instagram social media is one of the social media that is widely used in Indonesia and even in the world to foster friendship and communication between users. Instagram is also the social media that is most widely used as a means of advertising traders' products to consumers and potential new consumers at large.

4. Brand image.

Brand image What is meant here is the Caramia Store trademark image in the target market segment

Paradigms and Types of Research

This research is qualitative research which was prepared using a descriptive approach so that the presentation of the results can be carried out systematically and in detail, realistically and accurately according to the facts of the situation at the time of the research. Qualitative research also develops

questions through interviews with sources about what, what the actual incident was, and who was involved in the incident.

Research Subjects and Objects

The subject of this research is the @caramiastore.id account which operates via Instagram social media. Meanwhile, the subjects of this research consist of two groups, namely one admin and then the owner of the business @caramiastore.id Surabaya. Furthermore, the subjects of this research also came from informants who were followers (followers) from the @caramiastore.id account on Instagram as many as 3 people.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The main data source in this research is interviews. The sources who are the main data source for this research consist of two people representing caramiastore.id and three people representing consumers who are active on Instagram social media.

Marketing Communication Strategy

The following is a description of the interview results related to marketing communication strategies on Instagram. Interviews were conducted with the company, represented by one leader and two customer service people. The interview originates from the theory of marketing communication strategy expressed by Kotler (in Apriliya, 2017).

Advertising (Advertising)

Advertising is the main thing that was created by the head of the caramia store.id company, who also serves as director and manager. Based on the description of the interview results, it appears that the use of Instagram is a marketing communication strategy carried out by the caramia store.id company. This strategy makes the company's marketing communications able to penetrate consumers even though there are large-scale social restrictions due to Covid-19. With Instagram, consumers are not limited by distance or time and can be directed to direct sales (WhatsApp) or via Shopee e-commerce which is managed by Caramia Store.id.

Promotion

Promotion is one part of the marketing communication strategy implemented by the company via the Instagram account @caramiastore.id. This promotion is carried out when there are certain products that need to be sold in greater quantities, or when there are new products and products of special quality. Based on the description of the interview results, it appears that the promotion carried out by the company's Instagram account @caramiastore.id was really carried out seriously and made consumers interested so they immediately contacted the facility.direct message (DM) on the @caramiastore.id account. The private message in the form of DM was followed up by the admin by directing him to the action of purchasing or repurchasing, namely providing a link to the @caramiastore.id account on Shopee or directly via WA and Instagram.

Personal Selling

Personal selling is sales carried out directly by one @caramiastore.id company staff with its consumers. This is also done routinely by the company through its marketing steps on Instagram. Based on information from interviews, it appears that personal selling is sales that are routinely made to consumers who are just getting acquainted with the company's products and existing existing consumers. All consumer data is recorded and then used to market the company's products and notify consumers when there are promotional programs by the company. This means that the company will 'broadcast' messages via Instagram or WhatsApp to consumer numbers recorded on the company's computers.

Public Relations

Public Relations or public relations is one of the company's strategic steps @caramiastore.id to establish marketing communications and to handle complaints from consumers regarding products, services or anything related to the activities of companies that actively operate with strategies on Instagram in marketing their products. Every question will be answered and every complaint will be handled. Based on information from the interview results, it appears that questions from consumers addressed to the company will be examined and evaluated directly by the company leadership. Here, every question must be answered correctly and every complaint such as a receipt, goods purchased do not match what was ordered, errors in writing in the address will be attempted to get a solution as expected. So, implementing this public relations program is not only the responsibility of employees, in this case customer service, but also the responsibility of all employees.

Direct Marketing

Direct marketing is marketing that is carried out directly via live Instagram to create two-way communication that responds in real time and gives an impression of brand information.

Based on this information, using direct marketing in the form of live on Instagram will bring closer the relationship between sellers and buyers to build product trust. With live Instagram, you will answer consumer questions directly. When you go live on Instagram, your account followers will get a notification. Both when the live starts and when it ends. Apart from that, in the Instagram story section, the account that goes live will be second from the left. This creates an account online @Caramiastore will be easier for users to see and find.

Brand Image

Brand image What has been achieved by the company @caramiastore.id can be seen from the answers of resource persons from consumers on Instagram. Brand image can be measured by consumer perceptions of products and companies @caramiastore.id in two dimensions, namely physical factors and psychological factors (Ratri, 2007 in Iga Maulina Muliawati, Maya Retnasary, 2020). Interviews were conducted with five consumers and the results are detailed as follows:

Physical Factors of Marketing Communication Strategy

Physical factors are a form of output or result from advertisements displayed by the Instagram account @caramiastore.id to its followers. The physical form of the advertisement can be viewed based on

1) design, and 2) consumer impressions of the products shown in advertisements. Advertising design

There were sources who saw that colors tend to have a cheerful tone, such as light yellow, light green or bright purple. Of course, with a matching color scheme, the Instagram feed will be neatly arranged and the layout is pleasing to the eye, apart from that, the grid layout will be more aesthetic and consistent. by taking clear photos and maximum photo resolution. There are also sources who see a side of sleepwear that other stores don't have.

Product Impact

Advertisements displayed via the Instagram account @caramiastore.id also create a certain impression in the minds of consumers. Based on information obtained from sources obtained through interviews, it appears that consumers have the impression that the advertisements displayed by the Instagram account @caramiastore.id are quite interesting because on IG you rarely find shops online which specializes in selling pajama products. Likewise, consumers admit that the advertisement displayed by the Instagram account @caramiastore.id gives a special impression because in other stores there are no pajamas that are as good as those offered by caramia store.id. The advertisements designed and created by the Instagram account @caramiastore.id indeed seem creative and make consumers curious to look at other advertisements that have been previously broadcast on the Instagram account @caramiastore.id.

Psychological Factors

A. Consumer Impressions of Caramiastore.Id Advertising Design

Based on information from interviewed sources, it appears that consumers have a positive impression of the Instagram account @caramiastore.id. It means, the brand image which is owned by caramiastore.id has been well established because consumers see that the specialization of products offered by this shop is always consistently supported by low prices but with professional service. Consumers view caramiastore.id as a center for online fashion sales online, especially in the form of pajama products on IG.

B. Consumer Trust in Products at Caramiastore.Id

Based on statements from several sources, it appears that consumers, especially consumers who have been obtained through posting advertisements on the @caramiastore.id account on IG, admit that the products advertised by Caramia Store can be trusted. This is because the product received by consumers is close to reality or in accordance with the physical and quality of the product as published in the advertisement on the Instagram account @caramiastore.id. Consumers admit that the products advertised by the Instagram account @caramiastore.id can be trusted and the quality of the products has been proven through several purchases they have made. This means that even though the products published in Caramia Store advertisements are relatively cheap in the eyes of consumers, the Instagram account @caramiastore.id can maintain

consumer trust by guaranteeing quality and models that match what is published in advertisements on IG.

Consumer impressions of Caramiastore.id

Consumers, as well as followers of the Instagram account @caramiastore.id, of course have a special impression of the company which has always displayed various advertisements on the IG accounts it manages.

Based on the picture obtained from interviews with these sources, it appears that consumers, namely followers of the Instagram account @caramiastore.id, have a positive impression of the company. The company is described as a professional and reliable company as one of the pajama sellers on IG. Especially for followers, the Instagram account @caramiastore.id is synonymous with cheap but good quality pajamas and never disappoints its consumers.

CONCLUSIONS

Determining a strategy to build a brand image through the Instagram account @caramiastore.id consistently is the right choice in building the company's active participation with its consumers. Through this account, Caramia Store continues to develop social media functions with other functions as marketing communication media supported by WhatsApp social media to carry out advertising, promotion, personal selling and public relations functions. This social media instrument approach is able to build participatory communication through active interaction between Caramis Store and its partners.

Apart from that, the content on social media is able to build an impression of the product from a psychological aspect, creating the impression that it is a center for online fashion sales. There is consumer trust that the products advertised by Caramia Store can be trusted. This is because the product received by consumers is close to reality or in accordance with the physical and quality of the product as published in the Instagram account advertisement. Likewise, the company can be described as a professional and reliable company as one of the pajama sellers on IG. Especially for followers, the Instagram account @caramiastore.id is synonymous with cheap but good quality pajamas and never disappoints its consumers. Advertisements carried out by the Instagram account @caramiastore.id have attracted attention from consumers. Likewise, with a communication strategy in the form of promotions for goods sold on Instagram, this can increase the attention of consumers. The strategy in the form of personal selling steps has been able to bring closer the relationship between the company via the Instagram account @caramiastore.id and its consumers who are followers on Instagram. Finally, with a strategy in the form of public relations, consumer curiosity is met, and even all consumer complaints are resolved properly.

RECOMMENDATIONS

To the caramia store company, through advertising via the Instagram account @caramiastore.id it appears that the followers are giving Brand image a good company and able to improve extensive relationships with consumers. Therefore, companies should also use other social media to do things similar to what has been done on Instagram. For example, Caramia Store can start managing advertisements through videos on social media YouTube, Facebook and Tiktok as a means of carrying out marketing communication strategies and ultimately being able to increase Brand image from the company. To other researchers, other researchers who wish to conduct research similar to this research should also use a combination of quantitative observation techniques. This is so that research findings can be used as a means of measuring levels Brand image which is formed through the implementation of marketing communication strategies.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations, so it is necessary to carry out further research related to the topic of Building a Caramia Brand Image Through Circular Model Instagram @Caramiastore at Social Media in order to improve this research and add insight to readers.

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